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Anopheles darlingi (Culicidae)
mosquitoes from the Brazilian Amazon

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Research

Diversity of culturable bacteria isolated from the feces of wild *Anopheles darlingi*
(Culicidae) mosquitoes from the Brazilian Amazon

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1 **Abstract**

2 Microorganisms living in the midgut of *Anopheles* mosquitoes have been studied to fight
3 vector-borne diseases, such as malaria. Studies on the microbiota of the Neotropical
4 *Anopheles darlingi*, the most important Brazilian vector for malaria, have been reported
5 for the same purpose. Our aims were to isolate and identify culturable bacteria from *An.*
6 *darlingi* mosquito guts through their feces and to estimate the species richness and the
7 frequency distribution of the sampled bacteria. Sixty wild females of *An. darlingi*
8 mosquitoes were captured at two rural locations, near Porto Velho, Rondônia, Brazil.
9 Bacteria were isolated from mosquito feces, which were collected using cages which
10 permit the collection of feces on LB nutrient agar plates. Sixty bacterial colonies were
11 isolated and stored in glycerol at -80 °C. Bacteria were identified by sequencing their 16S
12 rRNA gene obtained using PCR and Sanger sequencing. To aid in species identification,
13 MALDI-TOF, VITEK®2 and BBL Crystal were used as complementary protocols. The
14 sequences obtained from the 60 bacterial isolates were compared to sequences deposited
15 in Genbank (NCBI) using BLAST. Homology greater than 97% between the query and
16 the subject was used as the criteria for assigning the identity of each isolate. Fourteen
17 species from 8 different genera were identified among the 60 isolates. The most frequent
18 species were *Serratia liquefaciens* (20%) and *Serratia marcescens* (15%). Due to their
19 established apathogenicity and according to previous studies, we suggest *Serratia* and
20 *Pantoea* species as suitable for paratransgenesis development to fight malaria in Brazilian
21 Amazon.

22

23 **Key words:** 16S rRNA. MALDI-TOF. Microbiota. Phylogenetic analyses. Malaria
24 vector.

25 **Introduction**

26 The use of intestinal microbes to control vector-borne diseases has been suggested
27 since the microbiota can be manipulated to reduce the competence of insects to transmit
28 pathogens, and especially, malaria parasites (Wang et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2020). Some
29 studies have supported strategies for manipulating the competence or fitness of insect
30 vectors, based on heterologous microorganisms or genetically modified microbial
31 symbionts (Wang et al., 2012; Arora and Douglas, 2017). And, lately, Gao et al. (2019)
32 presented a 20-years highlights review about the mosquito microbiota for blocking
33 pathogens transmissions, discussing the potential of using components of the microbiota
34 to fight mosquito-borne diseases.

35 Concerning malaria, a disease caused by *Plasmodium* sp., some researchers have
36 pointed out that malaria eradication cannot be achieved using current control methods.
37 Then, it is mandatory to develop a new generation of tools for global malaria eradication,
38 like those based on paratransgenesis, i.e., using bacteria to produce peptides that block the
39 development of the malaria parasite in the mosquito vector (Wang; Jacobs-Lorena, 2013;
40 Wilke; Marrelli, 2015; malERA, 2017), is highly necessary. Since bacteria present in the
41 gut of a mosquito vector and *Plasmodium* share the same environment during some part
42 of their lifespan, such bacteria may be engineered to interfere with parasite development
43 inside the digestive tract of the vector, thus disrupting the parasite's life cycle, preventing
44 transmission (Wang et al., 2017). Bear in mind all approaches to fight vector-borne
45 diseases should be integrated to achieve the malaria eradication (malERA, 2017).

46 Studies on the microbiota in mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles* have been
47 reported in recent years (e.g. Rani et al., 2009; Ngo et al., 2015, 2016; Krajacich et al.,
48 2018), and we also started to understand the microbiota of the Neotropical *Anopheles*
49 *darlingi* (Terenius et al., 2008; Villegas and Pimenta, 2014; Arruda et al., 2017).
50 Identification by metagenomics of bacteria associated to *An. darlingi* from Amazon

51 region have been reported during last decades, as follow: Terenius et al. (2008), identified
52 bacteria from 3 genera (*Aeromonas*, *Pantoea* and *Pseudomonas*) associated to *An.*
53 *darlingi*; Nilsson et al. (2019), identified several bacteria (OTUs) from non-lab breeding
54 sites and they suggest the genera *Escherichia/Shigella*, *Staphylococcus*, and
55 *Pseudomonas* as being commonly associated to the habitat of *An. darlingi*; and Oliveira
56 et al. (2020) reported the identification of 8 bacterial genera also associated to wild *An.*
57 *darlingi* (*Escherichia*, *Enterobacter*, *Asaia*, *Symploca*, *Pseudanabaena*, *Pseudomonas*,
58 *Xantomonas* e *Serratia*).

59 In a matter of fact, even though the metagenomic identification of bacterial species
60 is the most frequent approach in the literature, it is not enough to achieve a
61 paratransgenesis strategy to fight malaria or any other vector-borne disease. It is
62 mandatory to isolate culturable bacteria that should be amenable to genetic manipulation.
63 Thus, we have already reported the isolation of bacteria of the genera *Acinetobacter*,
64 *Staphylococcus*, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, and *Serratia* from *An. darlingi*, by applying a
65 simple culture-dependent method (Arruda et al., 2017).

66 Our study aimed to further isolate, identify and estimate species richness of
67 culturable bacteria present in the gut of *An. darlingi*, an important vector of malaria in the
68 Brazilian Amazon region, and thus, contribute to the development of biotechnological
69 tools needed to fight malaria and, potentially, other endemic diseases.

70

71 **Material and Methods**

72 **Mosquito collection**

73 Mosquitoes were captured at two rural locations near Porto Velho, Rondônia,
74 Brazil (08°48'56,8" S 63°42'4,2" W and 08°38'00,3" S 63°55'51,9"W). Captures were
75 carried out by the FIOCRUZ Rondônia field team between September to November/2014,

76 using a hand-held aspirator. Temperature and relative humidity were controlled during
77 transportation to the laboratory at FIOCRUZ Rondônia. *An. darlingi* were identified using
78 identification keys (Consoli and Oliveira, 1994) and we took sixty females selected for
79 bacterial sampling.

80 **Isolation of bacteria from *An. darlingi* feces**

81 Bacterial colonies were obtained directly from the feces of *An. darlingi* females
82 following the protocol described by Arruda et al., 2017. Feces from wild females
83 mosquitoes kept in a box with mesh in the bottom were collected by gravity directly on
84 nutrient LB (Luria-Bertani medium) agar plates, as described by Arruda et al., 2017. After
85 incubating the plates at 28 °C for 24 h, isolated bacterial colonies with different
86 morphologies were harvested from the petri dishes, transferred to new dishes to ensure
87 the production of pure cultures (streak plate method), as described by Arruda et al., 2017.
88 Sixty isolated bacterial colonies were stored individually in 15% glycerol at -80 °C.

89

90 **Identification of bacteria using 16S rRNA sequences**

91 Extraction of bacterial genomic DNA and amplification by PCR (Polymerase
92 Chain Reaction) of the 16S rRNA gene fragment was performed as described by Arruda
93 et al., 2017 [15]. Primers 16S08F (GYCCADACWCCTACGG) and 16S08R
94 (CACGAGCTGACGAC) were designed for amplifying a fragment containing regions
95 from V2 to V6 of the 16S rRNA gene. Amplicons from each isolated colony were purified
96 using the QIAquick Gel Extraction kit (QIAGEN, Co.).

97 Sequencing was performed using 20 µg of purified products at Fiocruz
98 Sequencing Platform (Plataforma Tecnológica de Genômica da Fiocruz-Subunidade
99 RPT01E - Sequenciamento de DNA – BH). The consensus sequences for the 16S rRNA

100 regions (V3, V4, V5 and V6 regions) of each isolated bacteria were assembled using four
101 to six reads in the PHRED-PHRAP-CONSED package (Ewing and Green, 1998; Ewing,
102 Hillier and Wendl, 1998; Green, 2009; Gordon and Green, 2013;
103 <http://www.phrap.org/phredphrapconsed.html>). The sequence for the V2 region of 16S
104 rRNA was eliminated of consensus sequences. For this assembly, each consensus was
105 read at least two times with a PHRED base quality above 30.

106 The nucleotide sequences with satisfactory quality in fasta format were aligned
107 using the MUSCLE alignment program (Edgar, 2004) on the MEGA7 software platform
108 (Kumar et al., 2016). After alignment of the consensus sequences of each bacteria, primer
109 sequences were manually trimmed. They were then submitted to BLASTN 2.7.0
110 software, choosing the search set: database Reference RNA sequences
111 (refseq_rna) using Megablast (Optimize for highly similar sequences) (Zhang et al.,
112 2000;
113 [https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PROGRAM=blastn&PAGE_TYPE=BlastSearch](https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PROGRAM=blastn&PAGE_TYPE=BlastSearch&LINK_LOC=blasthome)
114 [h&LINK_LOC=blasthome](https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi?PROGRAM=blastn&PAGE_TYPE=BlastSearch&LINK_LOC=blasthome)). Reference sequences (RefSeq) is a curated non-redundant
115 sequence database of sequences (Pruitt, Tatusova and Maglott, 2007).

116 The results of the alignments performed in the BLASTN program had coverage
117 and identity values observed to assist in choosing the most similar rates. Alignments with
118 coverage and identity above 97% were considered and noted. The RDP Classifier (Wang
119 et al., 2007) and Seqmatch tool RDP
120 (https://rdp.cme.msu.edu/seqmatch/seqmatch_intro.jsp) were used along with SILVA
121 high quality ribosomal databases (SINA 1.2.11 on-line) (Pruesse et al., 2007; Quast et al.,
122 2013).

123 The taxonomic attributions were given to each isolate using two different
124 approaches. First, by determining the identities of all sequences using taxonomic

125 classifiers and secondly, a phylogenetic tree was constructed containing sequences
126 representative of the isolates and sequences with which the isolate showed the greatest
127 similarity in the consulted databases. Phylogenetic trees were used to refine the
128 taxonomic assignment for each isolate, resolving taxonomic conflicts found in classifiers
129 like the RDP classifier.

130

131 **Complementary analyses for bacterial identification**

132 Sixty preserved bacterial samples were sent for species identification using mass
133 spectrometry in MALDI-TOF (MALDI-TOF, VITEK MS-bioMerieux) at Medical
134 Laboratory Santa Luzia Corporation, Florianópolis - SC - Brazil (www.sluzia.com.br).
135 We adopted a 99% confidence level for species identification using MALDI-TOF
136 VITEK® MS (bioMerieux).

137 Samples that could not be identified using this technique were then sent for species
138 identification using VITEK®2 Systems equipment to LACEN in Porto Velho, Rondônia
139 and Santa Luzia Laboratory in Florianópolis, Santa Catarina. Samples were deposited at
140 Fiocruz Bacterial Collections as described in **(Supplementary File 1)**.

141

142 **Phylogenetic analyses**

143 Phylogenetic analyses were performed based on the Neighbor-Joining method
144 (Saitou and Nei, 1987) with a bootstrap of 1000 replicates. A nucleotide substitution
145 model test was performed to select the lowest BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion)
146 score. Thus, the best model for the dataset of the bacterial 16S rRNA region was obtained
147 when evolutionary distances were calculated using the Kimura 2-parameter method
148 (Kimura, 1980).

149 For the bacterial 16S rRNA region, phylogenetic analysis involved 67 nucleotide
150 sequences. All positions containing gaps and missing data were excluded for distance
151 estimation and the final data set was composed of 453 positions total. The result was a
152 single phylogenetic tree in which all the bacterial isolates are grouped with related
153 phylogenetic groups. Phylogenetic analyses were performed in MEGA7 software (Kumar
154 et al., 2016).

155

156 **Estimation of species richness and frequency**

157 Each insect gut has several habitats, regarding the physicochemical conditions in
158 the lumen of different gut compartments, and they will be colonized by different species
159 of bacteria according to the feeding site and ecological interactions (Engel and Moran,
160 2013). Besides that, Valiente Moro et al. (2013), for instance, reported the relative
161 abundance of isolates according to the sampling sites and the isolation media. They
162 showed the isolation procedure using LBm medium sampled the most diverse bacterial
163 composition in comparison to other isolation media. Therefore, the gut bacteria
164 ecosystem may be understood as a set of insect guts, with a variety of habitats, where
165 each insect should be seen as an island that has a fast transient dynamic of colonization
166 and competitive displacement. In this point of view, the assembly of bacteria species and
167 their species richness was estimated based on the number of bacteria isolates from 60
168 wild females of *An. darlingi*. Thus, species richness was defined as the number of species
169 present in a community (Begon et al 2006), recovered by applying a simple methodology
170 to collect culturable bacteria from feces of *An. darlingi* (Arruda et al 2017). The species
171 frequency was determined based on the number of times a species was recorded out of
172 the total number of colonies sampled (Santos, 2003), after which the species were sorted
173 according to frequency.

174

175 **Results**

176 Mosquitoes were captured at two rural locations near Porto Velho, Rondônia,
177 Brazil (08°48'56,8" S 63°42'4,2" W and 08°38'00,3" S 63°55'51,9"W). Captures were
178 carried out by the FIOCRUZ Rondônia field team between September to November/2014,
179 using a hand-held aspirator. *An. darlingi* were identified using identification keys
180 (Consoli and Oliveira, 1994) and we took sixty females selected for bacterial sampling.

181 Sixty bacterial colonies were sampled from the feces of *An. darlingi* female
182 mosquitoes caught in the wild using LB culture medium. Sixty PCR reactions were
183 performed to amplify the 16S rRNA partial region, 54 were amplified to the expected
184 size, approximately 700 bp. PCR reactions for bacteria isolates labeled as 26, 45, 53, 54,
185 57 e 58 did not amplify for the 16S rRNA region, so they are not indicated in the
186 phylogenetic tree (Fig. 1). However, these bacterial colonies are preserved in -80 °C and
187 available at Microbiology Lab/FIOCRUZ Rondônia.

188 The sequences showed similarities above 98% when compared to other sequences
189 deposited in the following databases: RefSeq_rna, BLASTN 2.7.0, RDP Classifier,
190 Seqmatch RDP and Silva high quality ribosomal database, and fifty sequences were
191 deposited in GenBank (Supplementary File 1). In addition, they presented phylogenetic
192 grouping consistent with bootstrap values above 95% over 1000 bootstrap iterations.

193 All the sixty bacterial isolates were also analyzed using other techniques, such as
194 MALDI-TOF VITEK® MS (bioMerieux), VITEK®2 (bioMerieux), BD BBL™
195 Crystal™ identification systems, for complementary species identification
196 (Supplementary Files 1 and 2). According to these findings: 33 bacteria isolates were
197 identified using MALDI-TOF VITEK® MS (bioMerieux), with 99% of confidence level
198 (Supplementary File 2), two bacteria isolates were identified applying VITEK®2

199 (bioMérieux), 1 bacteria isolate was identified by BD BBL™ Crystal™ identification
200 system. We highlight the identification of bacteria isolates labeled as 26 (*Klebsiella*
201 *pneumoniae*), 45, 53 and 54 (*Serratia liquefaciens*) were just identified by MALDI-TOF
202 VITEK® MS (bioMérieux) method and also we defined as non-identified the isolates
203 labeled as Bacteria 57 and 58 because they did not reach an acceptable confidence level
204 in MALDI-TOF identification. Thus, 24 bacteria isolates could not perform this second
205 protocol for different reasons, for example, bacteria isolates labeled as 1, 5, 9 and 19 died
206 in transportation to Santa Luzia Laboratory in Florianópolis, Santa Catarina
207 (Supplementary File 1). Despite this fact, these bacterial colonies are preserved in -80 °C
208 and available at Microbiology Lab/FIOCRUZ Rondônia.

209 The isolate labeled as Bacteria 2 was identified as *Pantoea dispersa* and the
210 isolates labeled as Bacteria 28, 33 and 36 were identified as *Pantoea* sp. (Supplementary
211 file 1 and Fig. 1). The isolates labeled as Bacteria 20, 25 and 39 were identified as
212 *Cedecea* sp. (Supplementary file 1 and Fig. 1). Both genera should be reexamined to find
213 their species, soon.

214 Upon association of the three techniques used to identify the bacterial species, we
215 found 2 phyla (Firmicute and Proteobacteria), covering 4 families (Enterobacteriaceae,
216 Staphylococcaceae, Moraxellaceae and Burkholderiaceae) and 8 genera (*Acinetobacter*,
217 *Burkholderia*, *Cedecea*, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Pantoea*, *Serratia* and *Staphylococcus*)
218 (Supplementary file 1).

219 We found a richness of 14 culturable bacteria species in the feces of wild *An.*
220 *darlingi* females from the Brazilian Amazon. The frequency distribution of the identified
221 species suggests the existence of three groups: a frequent group composed of *S.*
222 *liquefaciens*, *S. marcescens*, *Enterobacter cloacae* complex and *Acinetobacter*
223 *baumannii*; an intermediate group, composed of *Staphylococcus sciuri*, *Pantoea* sp.,

224 *Cedecea* sp. and *Staphylococcus warneri* and, finally, an infrequent group with six other
225 uncommon species (Fig. 2). It is important to notice that we have two isolates that were
226 not identified (Bacteria 57 and 58) and also the bacterial colony collection method
227 previously described only reports the presence of the species of microorganisms
228 associated with the digestive tract of *An. darlingi* and the frequency with which it was
229 recorded in Petri dishes. Thus, the colony collection method does not allow us to estimate
230 the abundance (number of microorganisms in the digestive tract of *An. darlingi*) or
231 density (CFU/ μ L) of microorganisms in the digestive tract of the mosquito.

232 **Discussion**

233 Some studies previously have used LB medium to isolate bacteria from the gut
234 of *Aedes* and *Anopheles* species (Chen et al., 2017 and Rani et al., 2009). Valiente-Moro
235 et al. (2013), while investigating bacteria from wild *Aedes albopictus*, compared the
236 diversity of bacteria recovered in three different culture media and, according to their
237 results, the isolation procedure using LB medium registered more than twice the bacterial
238 richness as other culture media. Isolation of microorganisms from animal feces for a
239 variety of purposes, such as the identification of pathogens or biotechnological interests
240 by microbiological analysis, is a widely performed approach and several techniques have
241 been applied both for the collection of feces and for the isolation of microorganisms
242 contained within them (Anvisa, 2004; Chen et al., 2016; Tobias et al., 2016). Regarding
243 small animals such as insects, more specifically mosquitoes, there is a lack of data and
244 few established methodologies to perform the collection of culturable microorganisms
245 contained in their feces.

246 Microbiota associated with the genus *Anopheles* have been investigated to
247 describe the microbial diversity that colonizes the mosquitoes' gut, who are often vectors
248 of diseases. The Enterobacteriaceae family was the most frequent, as in the study by

249 Boissière et al. (2012), who detected a higher frequency of Enterobacteriaceae bacteria in
250 *An. gambiae*'s midgut, for instance. Despite the growing interest of the scientific
251 community on the subject, Villegas and Pimenta (2014) cited the lack of information
252 about the bacterial microbiota of Neotropical *Anopheles* related to mosquitoes' gut.

253 The bacterial genera from *An. darlingi* feces found in the present study were
254 recovered using LB agar medium. They were also found in other wild *Anopheles* species
255 (Table 1). However, Chavshin et al. (2012), using BH agar culture medium isolated 5
256 different genera of bacteria from *An. stephensi*: *Pseudomonas*, *Alcaligenes*, *Bordetella*,
257 *Myroides* and *Aeromonas*. In this context, Valiente-Moro et al. (2013) demonstrated that
258 the composition of the culture medium affects the variety of recovered microorganisms.
259 Therefore, when using a culture medium different from LB, it is possible that different
260 species of microorganisms would be recovered from the feces of *An. darlingi*.

261 Preliminary data from this study was published, reporting the identification of 5
262 genera of bacteria that were isolated from *An. darlingi* feces: *Acinetobacter*,
263 *Staphylococcus*, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella* and *Serratia* (Arruda et al., 2017). In addition,
264 like Terenius et al. (2008), *Pantoea* was also identified in the feces of *An. darlingi* in the
265 present study. Now, we report 8 genera of bacteria, of which 5 genera had not yet been
266 reported for neotropical *Anopheles*, thus, updating bacterial genera associated with
267 *Anopheles* in the Americas.

268 Terenius et al. (2008) described 3 genera of bacteria (*Aeromonas*, *Pantoea* and
269 *Pseudomonas*) and Oliveira et al. (2020) found out 8 genera (*Escherichia*, *Enterobacter*,
270 *Asaia*, *Symploca*, *Pseudanabaena*, *Pseudomonas*, *Xantomonas* and *Serratia*) associated
271 to *An. darlingi*. Both studies carried out a protocol based on PCR amplification of 16S
272 rRNA region, without any isolation of the microorganisms from wild-type mosquitoes
273 fed with blood. The same bacterial genera presented by Terenius et al. (2008) were also

274 identified as being associated with *An. gambiae* and *An. stephensi* (Chavshin et al., 2012;
275 Djadid et al., 2011; Osei-Poku , 2012; Straif et al., 1998).

276 Fourteen bacterial species were identified from the feces of wild females of *An.*
277 *darlingi* from the Brazilian Amazon region. However, we suggest that bacterial species
278 belonging to the genera *Pantoea* and *Serratia* should be carefully examined for
279 developing paratransgenetic approaches into natural ecosystems. Our suggestion is based
280 on in the following criteria: bacteria should be non-pathogenic to humans and animals
281 and those that have been previously cultivated in vitro (Wang and Jacobs-Lorena, 2013;
282 Wilke and Marrelli, 2015).

283 Wang et al. (2012) reported that the number of *P. agglomerans* bacteria
284 increased more than 200 times during the first 2 days after blood feeding, a fact that is
285 advantageous because by increasing the number of bacteria, it is possible to increase the
286 expression of anti-*Plasmodium* peptides. In *Culex pipiens*, for instance, Gram-negative
287 bacteria also significantly increased after blood feedings when compared to bacteria
288 detected during sugar feedings (Zayed and Bream, 2004). In addition, Gram-negative
289 bacteria such as *P. agglomerans* reduce *P. falciparum* infection of *An. stephensi*
290 (Pumpuni et al., 1993). Moreover, these bacteria easily growth outside the digestive tract
291 of mosquitoes in aerobic laboratory conditions at 37 °C in LB agar medium and Nutrient
292 Agar medium, a fact that facilitates future manipulations that require cultivation. It is
293 important that a candidate for paratransgenesis grow well in aerobiosis since the purpose
294 is to disseminate the paratransgenic agent into the environment, which is aerobic. Other
295 authors have already suggested bacteria of these genera in performing paratransgenesis,
296 including paratransgenetic models as proofs of concept (WANG et al., 2012, 2017).

297 *Serratia marcescens* has no intrinsic antimicrobial resistance (CLSI, 2017) and
298 is considered an opportunistic pathogen. It has been used in paratransgenesis by other

299 authors (Gonzalez-Ceron et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2017, Oliveira et al. 2020). It was also
300 reported that an isolate of *S. marcescens*, a species that was also isolated in this study,
301 colonized the digestive tract of *Anopheles*, compromising the mosquito's survival and the
302 development of *Plasmodium*, thus making it a potential candidate for the development of
303 an intervention against malaria transmission (Bahia et al., 2014).

304 Planning an efficient way to deliver the engineered symbiont into the field is a
305 key criterion for performing paratransgenesis (Wang; Jacobs-Lorena, 2013). Then, taking
306 the fact that we successfully isolated bacteria from mosquito feces into account and also
307 the results reported by Bassene et al. (2020), we suggest microorganisms may also be
308 spread using natural sources of sugary feeding, such as nectar and exudate from plants.
309 This idea was deeply discussed in a recent review presented by Strand (2018). Thus, we
310 hypothesized that feeding sites, which are rich in nutrients and sugars, should be suitable
311 for breeding a variety of microorganisms. These feeding sites might be explored by
312 several insect species, when they may acquire a shared microbiota from feeding and body
313 contact with other insects, as well as simultaneously enriching the original microbiota due
314 to eliminating feces with new microorganism species over the feeding sources. Therefore,
315 natural food habitats may lead to the self-dissemination of paratransgenic microorganisms
316 ingested by mosquitoes.

317 We believe a successful dissemination of genetically modified microorganisms
318 may be achieved by using attractive sugar baits (Bilgo et al. 2018; Wang; Jacobs-Lorena,
319 2017; Khallaayoune et al., 2013). Actually, we are proposing a Microorganism Enriched
320 Sugar Bait (MESB) which can carry-on a self-dissemination of microorganisms from
321 feces by introducing microorganisms into the ecosystem using sugar baits (Schlein and
322 Pener, 1990).

323 It is crystal clear that the implementation of this delivery strategy needs to
324 establish a trade-off between risk and the need for new control strategies (Arora and
325 Douglas, 2017). Although the high potential of paratransgenesis to fight vector-borne
326 diseases, Huang et al. (2020) pointed out it is mandatory to observe regulatory
327 requirements, ethical standards and public acceptance to deal with releasing
328 microorganisms' strategies. MALERA (2017) recommended an initial and small-scale
329 study because there are environmental uncertainties associated with the widespread
330 distribution of technologies involving genetic manipulation of microorganisms which
331 must be understood before it would become a service or product.

332 Thus, a hypothetical monitoring protocol for tracking the development of the
333 conceptual model described must have at least eight steps, as follow: 1) The mosquito
334 will visit the MESB for food; 2) When it walks over the MESB to feed, it will ingest the
335 microorganisms (including the engineered target); 3) These microorganisms will be
336 dispersed to other natural feeding sources; 4) Natural sugary sources (nectar and exudate
337 from plants) provide the ecological conditions and resources required for microorganisms
338 from MESB; 5) Other mosquitoes, when visiting the natural sugary sources colonized by
339 microorganisms from MESB will also be contaminated by these new microorganisms. 6)
340 This second group of mosquitoes will again disperse clones of microorganisms from
341 MESB to new natural sugary sources; 7) A dissemination system will be established in
342 the natural ecosystem and the MESB microorganisms will become part of the mosquito
343 microbiota; 8) Finally, MESB microorganisms will be widespread in the whole ecosystem
344 and would fight *Plasmodium* inside the mosquitoes' midguts, preventing the transmission
345 of the disease to humans.

346 As a bottom line, we assert that knowing the microorganism species contained
347 in the feces of anophelines is a strategy that can facilitate the investigation of microbiota

348 that pass through the insects' midgut, and perhaps this method can also be used as a
349 strategy for self-dissemination, in which mosquitoes inoculated with the microorganisms
350 of interest would disperse their paratransgenic agent-filled stools into the natural
351 ecosystem.

352 It is possible to isolate culturable bacteria from the feces of *An. darlingi*. Sixty
353 bacteria were isolated and 54 were identified with 16S rRNA region and biochemically,
354 and then characterized into eight genera. We identified a species richness of 14 bacterial
355 species, the most frequent being *Serratia liquefaciens*, *Enterobacter cloacae* complex,
356 *Serratia marcescens*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*.

357 We also report five new records of bacteria associated with *Anopheles* in the
358 Americas: *Staphylococcus*, *Burkholderia*, *Cedecea*, *Klebsiella* and *Acinetobacter*.

359 Finally, we suggest that some bacterial species belonging to the genera *Pantoea*
360 and *Serratia* should be examined with the intent of developing paratransgenic
361 approaches to control malaria in the Brazilian Amazon based on MESB and linked with
362 the self-dissemination of microorganisms from feces into natural ecosystems.

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374

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545

546 **Table 1.** Previous reports of bacterial genera associated with *Anopheles*

Phylum / Class / Family / Genus of bacteria reported	Wild species / Author
FIRMICUTES/Bacilli Staphylococcaceae <i>Staphylococcus</i>	<i>An. culicifacies</i> (Chavshin et al., 2014)
PROTEOBACTERIA/Betaproteobacteria Burkholderiaceae <i>Burkholderia</i>	<i>An. gambiae</i> (Boissière et al., 2012)
PROTEOBACTERIA/Gammaproteobacteria Enterobacteriaceae <i>Cedecea</i>	<i>An. funestus</i> (Straif et al., 1998) <i>An. gambiae</i> (Straif et al., 1998)
<i>Enterobacter</i>	<i>An. albimanus</i> (Gonzalez-Ceron et al., 2003) <i>An. stephensi</i> (Rani et al., 2009)
<i>Klebsiella</i>	<i>An. funestus</i> (Straif et al., 1998) <i>An. gambiae</i> (Straif et al., 1998) <i>An. stephensi</i> (Jadin, 1967) <i>An. durene</i> (Jadin et al., 1966)
<i>Pantoea</i>	<i>An. stephensi</i> (Djadid et al., 2011) <i>An. gambiae</i> (Lindh et al., 2008) <i>An. gambiae</i> (Straif et al., 1998) <i>An. funestus</i> (Straif et al., 1998) <i>An. darlingi</i> (Terenius et al., 2008)
<i>Serratia</i>	<i>An. arabiensis</i> (Lindh et al., 2005) <i>An. albimanus</i> (Gonzalez-Ceron et al., 2003) <i>An. stephensi</i> (Jadin, 1967) <i>An. stephensi</i> (Rani et al., 2009) <i>An. darlingi</i> (Oliveira et al., 2020)
PROTEOBACTERIA/Gammaproteobacteria/ Moraxellaceae	

Acinetobacter

An. funestus (Osei-Poku, 2012)
An. stephensi (Rani et al., 2009)
An. claviger (Raharimalala et al., 2016)
An. maculipennis (Raharimalala et al., 2016)
An. plumbeus (Raharimalala et al., 2016)

547

548

549 **Fig. 1.** Phylogenetic tree for partial 16S rRNA sequence of bacterial isolates from the
550 feces of *Anopheles darlingi* females. The numbers on the branches of the tree indicate the
551 bootstrap value found from 1000 reps. For this analysis, 67 nucleotide sequences were
552 used. All positions containing gaps and missing data have been deleted. There were 453
553 positions at the end of the dataset. Performed in Mega Software 7.0.14. ● GenBank
554 reference; ○ Bacteria identified with 16S rRNA and MALDI-TOF; △ Bacteria identified
555 with 16S rRNA and biochemically (VITEK 2 or BD BBL™ Crystal™); □ Bacteria
556 identified with 16S rRNA alone. Bacteria isolates labeled as 26, 45, 53, 54, 57, 58 were
557 not considered in this construction because they did not have any closely related taxon in
558 GenBank

559

560 **Fig. 2.** Frequency distribution of the bacterial species isolated (N=60) from the feces of
561 *Anopheles darlingi* females in Porto Velho, RO. Bacteria isolates 57 and 58 were
562 determined as non-identified

563

564